

A description of the male of *Globicornis (Hadrotoma) semilimbata* (Pic, 1906) (Coleoptera: Dermestidae: Megatominae)

J. Háva

Private Entomological Laboratory & Collection

Rýznerova 37/37, Únětice u Prahy, Prague-west CZ-252 62 Czech Republic

e-mail: jh.dermestidae@volny.cz

ORCID 0000-0001-8076-9538

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Abstract. The male of *Globicornis (Hadrotoma) semilimbata* (Pic, 1906) is described, illustrated, commented and newly recorded from Macedonia.

Introduction

The aim of the present paper is to describe the morphology of the male of *Globicornis (Hadrotoma) semilimbata*. So far only a single female of the taxon, the holotype, has been described, which was collected in Greece and described by Pic in 1906.

The species was originally described in the genus *Hadrotoma*. Mroczkowski (1968) transferred the species to the genus *Globicornis* subgenus *Hadrotoma* as *Globicornis (Hadrotoma) corticalis* var. *semilimbata*. Háva (2007) stated it as valid species *G. (H.) semilimbata*.

In this work, the description of the species *Globicornis (Hadrotoma) semilimbata* is supplemented with a description of the male characteristics.

Materials and methods

The size of the beetles or of their body parts can be useful in species recognition and thus, the following measurements were made (in mm):

total length (TL) - linear distance from anterior margin of pronotum to apex of elytra.

elytral width (EW) - maximum linear transverse distance.

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Photographs were made with a Canon EOS 550 D camera, and the images were modified with Helicon Focus 7.7.5. software.

Acronyms of material depositories:

JHAC - collection of Jiří Háva (Únětice u Prahy, Prague-West, Czech Republic);

JSPC - collection of Jiří Stanovský (Ostrava; Czech Republic);

MNHN - collection of Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle (Paris, France);

RSPC - collection of Rudolf Schuh (Katzelsdorf, Austria).

Results

Globicornis (Hadrotoma) semilimbata (Pic, 1906)

Figs 1-8

Hadrotoma corticalis var. *semilimbata* Pic, 1906: 9.

Globicornis corticalis var. *semilimbata*, Mroczkowski, 1968: 115.

Globicornis semilimbata, Háva, 2007: 57.

Original description of female holotype by Pic (1906): “Foncé, ave cle pourtour externe des élytres et une étroite bordure suturale postérieure roussatre, tibias et tarses roux. Grèce: Sudena en Morée (ex Holtz).”

Description of male. Body slightly convex, elongated (Fig. 4), measurements: TL 3.6-4.0 mm, EW 1.8-2.0 mm. Dorsal and ventral parts covered by recumbent, yellow setation.

Head visible from above; integument of head is dark-brown; densely punctured. Eyes large, and convex without internal emargination. Median ocellus is present. Antenna has 10 antennomeres (Fig. 5). Antennal club with three antennomeres. Terminal antennomere in male (Fig. 5), in female is short and triangular. All antennomeres brown and are covered with erect brown setation. Palpomeres brown.

Pronotum dark-brown, coarsely punctured; medially with two depressions (Fig. 6). Posterior parts slightly dentate. Pronotal dorsal

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rim of antennal fossa of male slightly visible from above, while in female it is less visible.

Scutellum small, triangular with large punctures.

Elytra brown in first 1/3 laterally with reddish fascia (Fig. 2); entire area is sparsely punctured and covered by brown setation. Epipleuron brown with yellow setation.

Abdominal ventrites I-V with surfaces of integument dark-brown, finely punctured, and covered by yellow setation.

Legs brown with short yellow setation.

Pygidium brown, with short yellow setation.

Male genitalia (Fig. 7).

Type material. Holotype (♀): „Sudená, Morea, Holtz“ [= Kalavryta] / „Type“ / „TYPE“ / „H. corticalis v. semilimbata Pic“ - MNHN.

Material examined: 1 ♂, 4 ♀♀, Greece, Peloponnes: Ilia, Erymanthos mts. (S), 1.5 km NNW Orini, 1290-1370 m, 9.5.2013, Schuh lgt., J. Háva det. - RSPC, JHAC; 1 ♂, Greece, Peloponnesos, 40 km SE Tripoli, Umg. Agios Petros, 900-1160 m, 22.iii.1997, V. Assing lgt., - JHAC; 2 ♀♀, GR, Pelop. m., Mt. Taigetos, Poliana, 17-18.6.1974, Horák+Švihla lgt., J. Háva det. - JHAC; 1 ♀, Greece, S Kozani, Livadero env., 15.5.2014, Snížek lgt. - JHAC; 1 ♀, Greece, Western Macedonia, 4 km NW of Deskati, 1500 m, 39°56'N 21°46'E, 1.6.2015, O. Konvička lgt. - JHAC; 1 ♀, GR, Ioánina, Notia Pindos Mts., 1420 m, Metsovo env., meadows, 13.6.2012, B. Zbuzek lgt., - JHAC; 1 ♀, Greece, Macedonia, Mt. Trikláριο, 7 km N of Andartikó, 40°47.52'N 21°14.3'E, 1540 m, 1.6.2007, P. Kabátek lgt. - JHAC; 1 ♀, Greece, Pel., Alonistaina env., 1200-1400 m, 37°39'N, 22°12'E, 1-5.6.2009, Zd. Švec lgt. - JHAC; 2 spec., Macedonia, Bistra planina, Lazaropole, 1348 m, 22.5.2017, J. Stanovský lgt., J. Háva det. - JSPC, JHAC.

Differential diagnosis. The species is very similar to *G. (H.) corticalis* (Eichhoff, 1863) but differs from it by the reddish anterolateral elytral fascia, structure of antennae and male genitalia.

Distribution. A species known only from Greece, new to Macedonia. Háva & Herrmann (2017) erroneously recorded it from Croatia.

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Figs 1-3. *Globicornis (Hadrotoma) semilimbata* (Pic, 1906), holotype (♀): 1. habitus, dorsal aspect; 2. habitus, lateral aspect; 3. holotype labels.

Figs 4-8. *Globicornis (Hadrotoma) semilimbata* (Pic, 1906): 4. habitus of male, dorsal aspect; 5. antenna of male; 6. pronotum; 7. male genitalia; 8. female antennal club.

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